

Identification of amino acids on thin layer chromatograms by modified ninhydrin reagent

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Abstract : Spray reagents are very useful for detecting amino acids on thin layer chromatoplates. It is well known that ninhydrin is most widely used as a spray reagent for identification of amino acids due to its high sensitivity, although it produces same purple/violet color with all amino acids, except in two cases : proline and hydroxy proline however give a yellow color. A new modified ninhydrin spray reagent (2-furoic acid) with moderately high sensitivity (0.05–1.00 µg) for easy and rapid identification of amino acids on thin layer chromatography plates has been introduced. The reagent is capable of developing various distinguishable colors with many of them. The color pictures of the chromatograms by digital camera are also included to demonstrate the different colors. A probable mechanism for such color formation has also been proposed.

Keywords : Thin layer chromatography, amino acids, 2-furoic acid, ninhydrin.

Introduction

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) has been applied extensively for the identification of amino acids using various specific and non-specific spray reagents¹⁻²³ on chromatograms because amino acids are the basic units of proteins and polypeptides and they are also present in the free state in numerous natural products. Formation of similar color (purple/violet) with all amino acids except proline and hydroxy proline (yellow color obtained) by ninhydrin alone possesses a serious problem for their identification. But due to its high sensitivity²⁴ ninhydrin has wide application for amino acid detection. An effort has been made in the present work to solve this problem by using a reagent which can give various distinguishable colors with most of the amino acids in presence of ninhydrin on silica gel G TLC plates with moderately high sensitivity (0.05–1.00 µg). The sensitivities are comparable to other reagents so far introduced¹⁻²³ and more sensitive in many occasions than some other reagents referred here^{1,10,13-15,17-19} (Table 1). A probable mechanism for such color formation and the color pictures of the chromatograms by digital camera are also included here.

Table 1. Sensitivities of the different reagents used for the color formation on TLC plates

Spray reagent/s	Detection limit (µg)	Ref.
Dichlorodicyano- <i>p</i> -benzoquinone (DDQ)	0.1–1.0	1
3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid + ninhydrin	0.01–1.0	2
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde + ninhydrin	0.01–1.0	3
<i>N</i> -Cyanoguanidine + ninhydrin	0.03–1.0	4
2,3-Dichloro-1,4-naphthaquinone + isatin	0.01–0.3	5
Fluorescein isothiocyanate + ninhydrin	0.5–1.0	10
(i) 1,3-Indanedione + ninhydrin	(i) 0.1–0.3	11
(ii) <i>o</i> -Mercaptobenzoic acid + ninhydrin	(ii) 0.05–0.2	
(i) Oxalic acid + ninhydrin	(i) 0.04–0.2	12
(ii) Dithiooxamide + ninhydrin	(ii) 0.1–0.2	
(iii) Dithizone + ninhydrin	(iii) 0.08–0.2	

Table-1 (contd.)

(i) Orthophosphoric acid + ninhydrin	(i) 0.05–1.0	13
(ii) Sulfuric acid + ninhydrin	(ii) 0.2–4.0	
(iii) Hydrochloric acid + ninhydrin	(iii) 0.2–1.0	
(iv) Glacial acetic acid + ninhydrin	(iv) 0.1–1.0	
D-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid + ninhydrin	0.2–2.0	14
5-Sulphosalicylic acid + ninhydrin	0.1–2.0	15
4-Hydroxyacetophenone + ninhydrin	0.01–1.0	16
(i) 4-Hydroxyacetophenone + isatin	(i) 0.1–1.0	17
(ii) 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde + isatin	(ii) 0.09–0.7	
2,3-Dichloro-1,4-naphthaquinone	0.25–10	18
4-Hydroxyacetophenone + isatin-5-sulphonic acid (Na salt)	0.1–2.0	19
N-Anthracenyl methyl L-methionine + ninhydrin	0.05–0.5	20
N-Anthracenyl methyl L-leucine + ninhydrin	0.1–0.5	21
(i) <i>p</i> -Fluorobenzoic acid + ninhydrin	(i) 0.01–1.0	22
(ii) <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid + ninhydrin	(ii) 0.01–1.0	
(iii) <i>p</i> -Iodobenzoic acid + ninhydrin	(iii) 0.01–1.0	
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde + ninhydrin	0.03–1.0	23

Results and discussion

From Table 2, it is observed that various distinguishable colors of the amino acids are developed before and after final heating with the reagent I. Color development is somewhat different almost in all the cases after second heating. The color pictures of the chromatograms are shown in the Figs. 1 and 2. The original color produced by ninhydrin itself (purple/violet) is changed to various distinguishable colors by 2-furoic acid in presence of ninhydrin before and after final heating but after final heating the colors are deepened in intensity. The detection limits are low before (0.10–1.00 μg) and after final heating (0.05–1.00 μg). So, the newly introduced spray reagent in combination with ninhydrin turns out to be very effective for the variation of colors and also for the detection of different amino acids on TLC plates.

The mechanism leading to such color formation is uncertain but a possibility may be ascertained as follows. A 'secondary amide' is first formed by the reaction of amino acid with the reagent I and this then forms coloring complex (C-T)²⁵ with ninhydrin (Scheme 1), colors of which are variable depending on the nature of amino acids. On the other hand, the 'secondary amide' may also undergo the reaction with ninhydrin in the following way (Scheme 1) to produce the complex A. Other possibility

Table 2. Color formation of amino acids on TLC plates with 2-furoic acid-ninhydrin

Amino acids	Reagent I + ninhydrin				Detection limit of ninhydrin ^a (μg)	R_f values ^b
	Cold condition (before second heating)		Hot condition (after second heating)			
	Color observed	Detection limit (μg)	Color observed	Detection limit (μg)		
Glycine (1)	Yellowish orange	0.30	Reddish orange	0.30	0.001	0.32
Alanine (2)	Reddish brown	0.80	Brownish red	0.50	0.009	0.37
Valine (3)	Reddish brown	0.80	Deep brownish red	0.80	0.010	0.45
Leucine (4)	Reddish pink	1.00	Deep brownish red	0.80	0.010	0.55
Isoleucine (5)	Reddish pink	1.00	Deep brownish red	1.00	0.200	0.53
Serine (6)	Reddish pink	0.50	Reddish brown	0.30	0.008	0.35
Threonine (7)	Light pink	1.00	Deep brownish red	1.00	0.050	0.37
Aspartic acid (8)	Light dirty yellow	1.00	Light brown	0.30	0.100	0.33
Asparagine (9)	Light yellow	0.80	Deep yellow	0.50	0.100	0.14
Glutamic acid (10)	Brownish pink	1.00	Reddish pink	0.80	0.040	0.35
Glutamine (11)	Reddish pink	1.00	Pinkish brown	0.80	0.100	0.15

Note

Table-2 (contd.)

Lysine (12)	Brownish violet	0.10	Dirty brownish yellow	0.05	0.005	0.03
Histidine (13)	Brownish violet	1.00	Brownish yellow	0.50	0.050	0.20
Arginine (14)	Light violet	1.00	Deep violet	0.10	0.010	0.02
Phenylalanine (15)	Deep brown	0.80	Reddish violet	0.80	0.050	0.58
Tyrosine (16)	Pinkish violet	1.00	Pink	0.80	0.030	0.57
Tryptophan (17)	Brownish purple	1.00	Brownish orange	0.80	0.050	0.62
Cysteine (18)	Light pink	1.00	Light brown	1.00	0.020	0.38
Cystine (19)	Light violet	1.00	Light brown	1.00	0.010	0.32
Methionine (20)	Pinkish brown	1.00	Deep reddish purple	0.30	0.010	0.51
Proline (21)	Lemon yellow	0.50	Yellow	0.10	0.100	0.26
Hydroxyproline (22)	Pinkish purple	0.30	Dirty yellow	0.10	0.050	0.34

^aRef. Stahl (1969).

^b*n*-Propanol : water = 70 : 30 (v/v).

Fig. 1. Color of amino acids with ninhydrin in presence of reagent I in cold condition.

Fig. 2. Color of amino acids with ninhydrin in presence of reagent I in hot condition.

is the reaction of amino acids (unreacted or derived from 'secondary amide') with ninhydrin in the usual way to produce Ruhemann Complex B (except for proline and hydroxyproline, Scheme 2). Since both complexes (A and B) are formed in unequal amounts depending on the nature of amino acids and also conditions of the experiment, we observed the variation of color contrast of the different amino acids.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Chromatography plates (20 × 20 cm; thickness 0.1 mm) were prepared with silica gel G (Merck, India) using Unoplan Coating apparatus (Shandon, London, UK). Photographs of the colored chromatograms were performed by Digital Camera (Nikon Coolpix L-25, China).

Reagents :

Standard amino acids were obtained from Sigma (USA) and *n*-propanol from Merck (India).

Reagent I : 0.25% 2-furoic acid (Acros Organics, Geel, Belgium) in ethanol.

Reagent II : 0.25% ninhydrin (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) in acetone.

Detection on TLC plates :

Standard solutions (1 mg mL⁻¹) of amino acids were prepared in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ phosphate buffer (pH 8.0) and spotted on the TLC plates by means of a graduated micropipette (5 μL). The solutions were diluted according to the required spot concentration. Plates were air-dried and subjected to TLC with *n*-propanol-water, 70 : 30 (v/v) as mobile phase. After development plates were dried and sprayed with the reagent I and then heated at 110 °C for 10 min in an oven. Plates were cooled and then sprayed with reagent II and colors were noted (Table 2). Colors were further observed after heating the plates at 110 °C for 10 min (Table 2). Colors were observed visually and the color pictures of chromatograms by digital camera are also recorded (Figs. 1 and 2). Detection limits for the

Scheme 1

Amino Acid + Ninhydrin

Scheme 2

amino acids after use of ninhydrin reagent alone is also given in Table 2.

Limit of detection :

The Limit of detection of amino acids were determined by spotting a standard solution (1 mg mL^{-1}) of the concerned amino acid on to the TLC plate, which was developed with mobile phase and spot was visualized using the reagent and ninhydrin as described in the above section. This process was repeated with successive dilution of the standard amino acids solutions until no detection was possible. The amount of amino acid just detectable was taken as detection limit.

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